

Imines. 1: Synthesis and Nucleophilic Additions on Conjugated Imines

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New conjugated imines have been synthesized from heterocyclic amines and aromatic aldehydes. HCN adds on these imines to give cyanoamines and sodiumborohydride reduces them to secondary amines.

RECENTLY the synthesis and nucleophilic addition reactions¹⁻³ (H^- , CN^- , $HC\equiv^-$) etc.) on imines and conjugated imines have been reported from these laboratories. The work has been extended to the study (Scheme-I) of benzylidene-2-thiazolyamines

Sodium borohydride in methanol reduces imines to the dihydro products (III). These can be oxidized back to imine with activated manganese dioxide in dry benzene.

The azomethine structure (I) was confirmed by IR and mass spectrum. IR spectrum (in KBr) of Ia

Scheme-I

- Ia, X = H; Y = H
 b, X = *p*-Cl; Y = H
 c, X = *p*-CH₃; Y = H
 d, X = *p*-Cl; Y = Ph
 e, X = H; Y = Ph
 f, X = *p*-NO₂; Y = Ph

- IIa, X = H; Y = H
 b, X = *p*-Cl; Y = H
 c, X = *p*-CH₃; Y = H
 d, X = *p*-Cl; Y = Ph

- IIIa, X = H; Y = H
 b, X = *p*-Cl; Y = H
 c, X = *p*-CH₃; Y = H
 d, X = *p*-Cl; Y = Ph

The benzylidene-2-thiazolyamines (I) were prepared from 2-aminothiazoles and corresponding aldehydes. Imines from 2-amino-4-phenyl thiazole and substituted benzaldehydes are yellow crystalline powders. *p*-Chloro and *p*-nitro benzaldehydes gave imines in 90% yield, while benzaldehyde gave a poor yield (20%). The pure sample of benzylidene-2-(4-phenyl) thiazolyamine from the crude resinous product was purified by column chromatography on silica gel followed by crystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether.

When imines (I) (in methanol) were treated with aqueous sodium cyanide and acetic acid, cyanoamines (II) are obtained in good yields.

showed the absorption for $-CH=N-$ from 1540 to 1595 cm^{-1} . The mass spectrum showed a parent peak at m/e 188 (M^+) and the base peak (M^+-1) at

m/e 187. The fragmentation pattern was similar to that of *N*-benzylidene aniline⁴.

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The peak at m/e 160 (m/e 187-HCN) arose from the rearrangement $(ABC^+) \rightarrow (AC)^+ + B^*$, where B represented the HCN radical. The other major peaks were at m/e 104, 85, 77 and 58. The peaks at m/e 85 and 77 were due to thiazole and phenyl rings respectively.

The structure of cyanoanil (II) finds further support from ir 3430 cm^{-1} ($-\text{NH}-$); 1596 cm^{-1} ($> \text{C} = \text{N}-$ ring) and 2245 cm^{-1} ($-\text{C} \equiv \text{N}$). The ir spectrum of dihydro products III showed the $-\text{NH}-$ absorption at a very low frequency i.e. $3250-3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Experimental

Preparation of imines

2-Amino thiazole (1.0 g.; 0.01 mole) dissolved in methanol (15 ml) was added to a methanolic solution of benzaldehyde (1.06 ml.; 0.01 mole) at room temperature with stirring. The light brown solid obtained was recrystallized from 50% methanol; m.p. 109° ; yield 80%.

The other imines of this series (Table 1) were prepared in the same manner.

* c.f. Q. N. Porter and J. Baldas; Mass Spectrometry of Heterocyclic compounds, Wiley Interscience, N. Y., 1971, p. 514.

Hydrocyanide addition to imines (I)

Benzylidene 2-aminothiazole (1.88 g.; 0.01 mole) was dissolved in ethanol (15 ml) and solution was made acidic by the addition of acetic acid (0.6 ml.; 0.01 mole). A solution of potassium cyanide (0.6 g.; 0.01 mole) in water (5 ml.) was added to the imine solution with continuous stirring at 0° . The white solid obtained was filtered, washed with water and dried. On crystallization from methanol it melts at 126° .

The other nitriles II (Table 2) were obtained in the same manner.

NaBH_4 reduction of imines (I)

NaBH_4 (1.0 g.; 0.03 mole) was added to a methanolic solution of benzylidene 2-aminothiazole Ia (3.96 g.; 0.02 mole) over a period of half an hour at $5^\circ-10^\circ$. After the complete addition of sodium borohydride the reaction mixture was kept overnight at room temperature. The excess of sodium borohydride was destroyed by the addition of water and the semi-solid product so obtained was extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporated. The solid so obtained was crystallized from methanol to give IIIa, m.p. 128° .

TABLE 1

Compound No.	X	Y	m.p. $^\circ\text{C}$	Yield	I.R. absorption of $-\text{CH}=\text{N}$	Molecular formula	Analysis%	
							Found	Calculated
Ia	H	H	109	80	1555 cm^{-1}	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{S}$	N, 14.71	14.89
Ib	<i>p</i> -Cl	H	125-26	85	1595 cm^{-1}	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{SCl}$	N, 12.44 Cl, 15.42	12.58 15.95
Ic	<i>p</i> - CH_3	H	124	85	1540 cm^{-1}	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{S}$	N, 13.75	13.86
Id	<i>p</i> -Cl	Ph	131-32	90	1595 cm^{-1}	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{SCl}$	N, 9.29 Cl, 11.81	9.38 11.92
Ie	<i>p</i> - NO_2	Ph	149-50	90	—	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3\text{SO}_2$	N, 13.55	13.59

Methanol was used as solvent of crystallization.

TABLE 2

Compd. No.	X	Y	m.p. of nitriles* $^\circ\text{C}$	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis%	
						Found	Calculated
IIa	H	H	126	80	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{N}_3\text{S}$	C, 61.10 H, 4.00 N, 19.25 S, 14.53	61.39 4.18 19.53 14.88
IIb	<i>p</i> -Cl	H	139-40	70	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{N}_3\text{SCl}$	C, 52.62 H, 3.02 N, 16.53	52.90 3.20 16.83
IIc	<i>p</i> - CH_3	H	163	75	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3\text{SCl}$	C, 62.54 H, 5.00 N, 18.15	62.88 5.24 18.34
II d	<i>p</i> -Cl	Ph	150	75	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_3\text{SCl}$	C, 65.89 H, 3.42 N, 12.62	66.12 3.68 12.90

* The nitriles were crystallized from methanol or light petroleum-ether.

TABLE 3

S.No.	X	Y	m.p. °C	Yield %	I.R. absorption of -NH	Molecular formula	Analysis %		
							Found	Calculated	
IIIa	H	H	128	85	3250 cm ⁻¹	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ S	C, H, N,	63.00 5.20 14.63	63.16 5.26 14.74
IIIb	<i>p</i> -Cl	H	133-34	90	3280 cm ⁻¹	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂ SCl	C, H, N, Cl,	53.80 4.40 11.91 15.30	53.88 4.45 12.02 15.04
IIIc	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	H	120	95	3250 cm ⁻¹	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ S	C, H, N,	64.70 5.80 13.68	64.75 5.85 13.77
IIId	<i>p</i> -Cl	Ph	105	90	3280 cm ⁻¹	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₂ SCl	C, H, N, Cl,	63.80 4.22 9.28 11.70	63.89 4.32 9.32 11.81

Methanol was used as solvent of crystallization.

The other dihydro compounds (Table 3) were prepared by the above method.

Manganese dioxide oxidation of III

Manganese dioxide (6 g.) (prepared according to Attenburrow *et al.*⁵) and dihydro compound (IIIa) (1.90 g.; 0.01 mole) were taken in dry benzene (20 ml) and the contents were refluxed for an hour and left overnight at room temperature. Benzene was removed under vacuum after filtering out the inorganic material and the residue so obtained was recrystallized from benzene-pet. ether to give light brown solid, m.p. 109°.

This product showed no depression in m.p. on mixing it with the authentic sample of benzylidene 2-aminothiazole.

The other dihydro compounds were oxidized in the similar manner and gave the corresponding imines.

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